

Competency-Based Approach (CBA) and School Results in Physical Education and Sports in Secondary Schools in Côte D'ivoire

Dosso Namode Alice Spouse Binat¹, Ganon Mamadou²

¹Doctor in CRIMINOLOGY, option: Criminal Psychology.
Peleforo Gon Coulibaly University, Faculty of Social Sciences

²Physical and Sports Education Teacher

Student in Master 2 Project Management and Humanitarian Logistics CHAIRE UNESCO - Côte d'Ivoire

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 14 February 2022	As part of the reflection on the Ivorian educational system, this work aims at analysing the relationship between the Competency-Based Approach (CBA) and school results in Abobo's secondary schools in Physical and Sports Education (PSE). In fact, through the CBA, young people acquire various skills (knowledge and know-how) but also social skills (interpersonal skills) that give them value in social life. On the methodological level, a questionnaire was submitted to 79 (seventy-nine) teachers, including forty (40) public and thirty-nine (39) private teachers in the commune of Abobo. In addition, four (4) and two (2) resource persons were interviewed, including the head of the Pedagogy and Continuing Education Office (PCEO) in Abidjan. A mixed approach was used through the quantitative and qualitative method. The data collected was processed with MS EXCEL software, which was also used for the input and production of tables and graphs. The results of this study revealed that CBA is practised in Abobo secondary schools by about 50.60% of the teachers selected. More than 72% of the teachers interviewed have at least five (5) years of experience in teaching Physical and Sports Education (PSE). Most of them have therefore practised the OBA (objective-based approach) since the CBA, in its evolution through the teaching levels, entered the second cycle from 2015. The survey still reveals that these teachers have the required level of pedagogical skills or sufficient subject knowledge to teach effectively with this approach. Only 02.53% of the teachers surveyed may not have the recommended skills. However, it appears that CBA does improve students' academic performance in terms of knowledge, skills and also social or life skills, which are by nature skills for autonomy and conformity to social rules.
Corresponding Author: Dosso Namode Alice Spouse Binat	Hence the use of the reference theory of social control, by Maurice Cusson (2015). It makes the school a situational and developmental prevention, effective in curbing deviance, delinquency and even criminality in young people.
KEYWORDS: CBA, Physical and Sports Education (PSE), School results, Education, Skills.	

INTRODUCTION

In Côte d'Ivoire, the school is in a state of disaster¹ because it is undermined by several evils such as: poor results in mass examinations; the phenomenon of early holidays in secondary schools; untimely strikes; overlapping university years; devalued diplomas such as Brevets of Superior Technicians

(BTS); unemployment among Ivorian graduates, which has reached 3,000 PhDs waiting to be recruited²; pedagogical approaches that are regularly changed; the thorny issue of adapting to the LMD system; etc. In reaction to this state of affairs, the various disciplines propose reflections so that the school, which is a generator of education, manages to play its

¹ STÉPHANE KIPRE: SCHOOL IS A DISASTER IN CÔTE D'IVOIRE

Posted on February 21, 2019 on

<http://ung.ci/2019/02/21/lecole-sinistree-cote-divoire/>

² <https://www.connectionivoirienne.net/2021/11/05/cote-divoire-affaire-3000-docteurs-sans-emplois-le-ministre-diawara-leur-conseille-le-prive-ou-lens-ou-la-patience>

role in socialisation. E. Durkheim (1999), in his definition, states that education is "the action exercised by the adult generations on those who are not yet mature for social life". For him, the aim of this education is to arouse and develop in the youngest a certain number of physical (know-how), intellectual (knowledge) and moral (self-knowledge) states. These skills will enable them to integrate into society in general, but also into the specific environment for which they are intended. For this reason, it remains an essential sector for all peoples. In this regard, Nelson Mandela, a famous African politician, maintained that "education is the most powerful weapon for changing the world."³

Education as a process of acquiring knowledge, skills and attitudes begins in the biological family, which has given rise to the term 'family education', which can be defined as the process by which a family raises and educates a child from birth to adulthood. The parents' role is to provide for the child's psychological and physical needs, protect the child from harm, and impart cultural and social skills and values. As early as 1969, Bowlby argued that the child develops a hierarchy of attachment relationships; this is based on the strength of the sense of security provided by each relationship with the caregiver, linked to the amount and quality of care given.⁴

In addition to the family, the society has set up a process of educating the child through school, through programmes and their contents but also their activities. In this regard, Koudou et al (2021), argues that education is an exclusively social phenomenon: it is a means of transmitting the data of social experience.

Thus, from an early age, the child is divided between family education and that instituted by the states through the school. This is known as school education. This education is perceived as the whole of the knowledge dispensed in schools from kindergarten to the end of secondary school. As an institution, the school's mission is to prepare children for social and professional life. This is the socialising value of education, as the French scientist Albert Jacquard says in this statement: The role of the school is to integrate a little man into the human community, to transform an individual into a person. Let us repeat: to educate is to e-ducere, to lead a young person out of himself, to make him exist in the exchanges he experiences with others.⁵

Education would lead the young person to his social roles. School education could also lead the learner to the future job to which he aspires through specific learning; this is why school education, based on government policies, is

carried out by education systems. The organisation of each country's system is a function of the orientation given by its governments. In Côte d'Ivoire, the education/training sector is under the supervision of two ministries:

The Ministry of National Education⁶, Technical Education and Vocational Training (MENET FP). This ministry is responsible for pre-school, general and technical education and vocational training. Pre-school is the first educational stage. It includes the petite, moyenne and grande section and gives direct access to the primary cycle. This cycle has a theoretical duration of six (06) years and is sanctioned by the Certificate of Elementary Primary Studies (CEPE). General secondary education consists of the first and second cycles. The first cycle runs from the sixth to the third grade and has a theoretical duration of four (04) years. It is sanctioned by the Brevet of Undergraduate Studies (BEPC). The second cycle runs from the second to the final year of secondary school and lasts for three (03) years and is sanctioned by the Baccalaureate (BAC).

As for technical education and vocational training, their mission is to respond to the needs of young people concerning their integration into working life on the one hand, and on the other, to fill the gap in qualified personnel in companies. In other words, technical education and vocational training should contribute to the socio-professional integration of young people, the development of human resources, the achievement of economic growth objectives and the reduction of poverty and unemployment.

The second ministry in charge of education in Côte d'Ivoire is the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (MESRS)⁷. This ministry is responsible for implementing the government's policy on higher education and scientific research. It groups together several universities and public and private grandes écoles.

Furthermore, the MENET FP, through its reforms, has adopted various pedagogical methods over the years in order to solve the problem of inefficiency in education. The most recent are the Objective-Based Approach (OBA) and Competency-Based Approach (CBA) currently in force.

The OBA proceeds by teaching broken down disciplinary contents by integrating the principles of the behaviourist model. This pedagogy is centred on the learning process, which involves stages from simple to complex, the reproduction of the model in similar situations and objectives defined in terms of observable behaviour.⁸

It is following numerous criticisms that this pedagogy has finally given way to the competency-based

These ministries are constantly being reshuffled and often have their scope reduced or expanded. Our information remains consistent with that in force until mid-2021.

⁷ Home - MESRSCI : enseignement.gouv.ci

⁸ https://wiki.teluq.ca/wikimedia/index.php/Approche_par_objectifs

³ Retrieved from this link:

fandumonde.com/2020/06/24/education-nelson-mandela/

⁴ Retrieved from Origins and Concepts of Attachment Theory | Cairn.info

⁵ Cf 100 quotes and thoughts on education - abc-citations

⁶ Ministry of National Education and Literacy - Côte d'Ivoire (education.gouv.ci)

approach (CBA), which is analysed in this study. According to P. Perrenoud (1998), this approach would be suitable for both good students and those with learning difficulties insofar as the development of competences in the school environment makes it possible to promote "the transfer of knowledge" to students who correctly assimilate knowledge and know-how in class but are unable to mobilise them outside the context of acquisition, on the one hand, and on the other hand, to interest those who do not adhere to decontextualised knowledge cut off from all practices. This new approach is based on the following main objectives:

-The learner is responsible for his or her own learning. The teacher is simply a facilitator;

-The learner learns when he/she is interacting with peers or the teacher;

-They learn when their learning is meaningful. In other words, the learner needs to know the purpose of everything he/she learns in school;

-He learns with the help of an adult or from real life experiences.

It was from 2002 onwards that CBA was gradually introduced into general education in Côte d'Ivoire, with the aim of reducing repetition and failure at school and developing learners' skills to enable them to cope with social situations.

The objective of this study was to analyse the relationship between CBA and academic results in Abobo secondary schools in Physical and Sports Education (PSE). In other words, we want to question the contribution of CBA on academic performance in PE; that is, we want to know if the competency-based approach is a wise pedagogical choice for the teaching of the sport discipline in that it allows for significant learning? In the sense that the person succeeds in learning, i.e. in acquiring knowledge, know-how and skills. That is to say that CBA would allow the young person to receive this education upstream from the family and downstream from school; which is socialising as advocated by authors and scientists.

Claude HALMOS, a French psychoanalyst, (2009), rightly speaks of delinquents as children who are sick of their education⁹: The testimonies of our survey cry out the suffering of professionals, young people and their parents who have difficulty locating the origin of delinquency. For a psychoanalyst, the answer is clear: delinquency comes from education. A delinquent, in fact, is someone who harms people, property or morals. By acts which are always very serious because, whatever their real importance, they call into question the very functioning of social life: (...) Why can't a delinquent integrate the social order? (...) the social law and its usefulness - (...) it is only an unpleasant obstacle to enjoyment (...) he does not manage to build reference points

and ideals capable of helping him to set limits for himself (...) because the control of his impulses, the consideration of others, the understanding of moral rules and the law are by no means natural and innate. They are learned. Step by step. Through education.

This study is part of the theoretical framework of social control. Faced with the issue of deviance, delinquency and even criminality, this theory makes it possible to gauge what the public authorities do and with what results?¹⁰ The question is: what are the public authorities and civil society doing and how effective are they? Borrowed from sociology, the criminologist uses the notion of social control to designate the efforts of all to keep delinquency within bearable limits. By social control we mean social regulation. It is the set of means implemented by the members of a society with the specific aim of containing or reducing the number and seriousness of offences and achieving a better socialisation of young people. For Cusson, the notion of social control is vast and encompasses preventive and repressive measures, as well as private and public actions and all the persuasive and dissuasive means employed. At the heart of sociology is the idea that all societies develop their own norms and exert pressure on their members to conform and sanction deviants. But most of the time, the sanction is not necessary because the anticipation of it is enough to curb the deviations. There are, therefore, means of formal social control and means of informal social control. Each type of means can be used for prevention. Education, as defined above, plays a role of informal social control and its capacity to 'prevent' is paramount in the socialisation process. Thus interaction within families, groups of friends, associations, in the work team, in local communities and especially exchanges at school: can be an effective situational and developmental prevention to curb delinquency and deviance.¹¹

In contrast to previous studies, the originality of my work lies in the fact that it highlights (in addition to the other skills acquired through CBA) the acquisition of social skills which, in turn, emphasise the notions of conformity to norms and the notion of autonomy and many other social skills that the young person can acquire through CBA. This part of CBA has not really been explored. These social skills, if acquired by the young person, would equip him or her (through the family and school education received) to be able to move away from delinquency and deviance.

METHODOLOGY

-Site and participants

The present study took place in the commune of Abobo. This commune is one of the thirteen (13) communes in the district of Abidjan. It is located to the north of the urban area (of Abidjan) with a surface area of 7,800 hectares. It is

⁹ Consulted on the net at this link [Délinquance: des enfants malades de leur éducation | Psychologies.com](#),

¹⁰ Maurice Cusson, 6th edition of his work "La criminologie

¹¹ Idem ; P 120.

bordered to the north by the commune of Anyama, to the south by the Banco forest, to the east by the commune of Cocody and to the west by the commune of Yopougon.

We chose this commune as our study area for several reasons. Firstly, our choice is explained by the fact that this commune currently has more than one hundred (100) schools, five (5) of which are public. Grammar schools 1&2 occupying the same site have more than ten thousand (10,000) students and twenty-eight (28) Physical and Sports Education (PSE) teachers.

We had an interview with the head of the Pedagogy and Continuing Education Office in Abidjan 4 and 2. This interview was a semi-directive interview using a guide as a tool. This guide, comprising three (03) items and nineteen (19) questions, made it possible to obtain useful information concerning, in particular, the CBA and previous approaches, the pedagogical activities of the Pedagogy and Continuing Education Office (PCEO) of Abidjan 4 in the field Private sector and thirty-nine (39) from the private sector, distributed among the schools as follows

Table 1: Distribution of teachers by school.

Schools	Status	Number of teachers interviewed
Lycée moderne 1	Public	15
Lycée moderne 2	Public	12
Lycée municipal	Public	13
Collège ANADOR	Private	10
Collège Sainte Foi	Private	07
G S FUSOS Cours Sociaux	Private	10
Groupe scolaire NANTI	Private	06
Collège IRIS	Private	06
TOTAL	Public & Private	79

Source: Field survey 2020.

The sampling was guided by the quota method. Thus, we observed more than a third of Physical and Sports Education (PSE) teachers working in Abobo's Secondary schools. In other words, we submitted our questionnaire to forty (40) teachers from the public sector and thirty-nine (39) from the private sector.

-Data collection techniques, analysis and processing

The qualitative method enabled us to collect and analyse the opinions, attitudes and behaviour of the teachers and pupils we met. We were able to identify the situation of the teacher at the individual level and that of the students during the teaching-learning process. We delved into the world of the teacher by exploring phenomena such as the teacher's posture,

gestures and movements as well as the students' involvement during learning.

The quantitative method was useful in the statistical processing of the data. It allowed us to process the information collected on the questions related to the students' grades in the two experimental tests; this facilitated the interpretation of the results.

We used manual and then computer processing of the collected data. We first manually checked that all questionnaires were correctly filled in by the respondents before processing the data on a computer level. MS EXCEL was used for data entry and for the production of tables and graphs. For the qualitative data, we used content analysis.

RESULTS

A- Practice of CBA in secondary schools - Status of Physical and Sports Education (PSE) teachers

Table 2: Distribution of respondents according to teacher's professional status

Status	Number	Frequency (%)
Public	40	50,6
Private	39	49,4
Total	79	100

Source: Field survey, 2020

Table 2 shows that out of seventy-nine (79) teachers surveyed, forty (40) obtained the Certificate of Aptitude for Teaching Physical Education and Sports (CAPEPS) after four years of study at the INJS, i.e. 50.60%.

Table 3: Continuing training of respondents working in private practice

Did you attend at least one training course at the INJS?	Number	Frequencies (%)
Yes	37	94,9
No	02	05,1
Total	39	100

Source: Field survey, 2020

Table 3 presents thirty-nine (39) teachers from public schools who have or have not received a minimum of training at INJS to teach Physical and Sports Education. It can be seen that almost 95% of these teachers have had at least one training course in teaching Physical and Sports Education.

These two tables show that almost all Physical and Sports Education teachers have teaching skills. They are therefore capable of creating meaningful and learning didactic situations and of developing formative observation.

In other words, their mastery of the principles of CBA has enabled them to derive maximum benefit from the application of this approach on the one hand, and on the other to assess the pupils' achievements after learning.

In our sample, only 02.53% of teachers might not have sufficient pedagogical skills or subject knowledge to teach effectively. However, this low rate could not discredit the findings of this study.

B- Knowledge and use of CBA and/or OBA

Table 4: Knowledge of CBA and/or OBA

Do you know CBA and/or OBA ?	CBA	Frequen cy (%)	OBA	Frequency (%)
Yes	79	100	68	86,07
No	00	00	11	13,93

Source: Field survey, 2020

Table 4 shows all teachers with knowledge of CBA and/or OBA. Indeed, all the respondents claim to be familiar with the competency-based approach and 86.07% with objective-based teaching. Eleven teachers had never heard of the OBA. The analysis of the results showed that these were teachers with less than five years' experience.

Table 5: Frequency of use of CBA and/or OBA

Do you use CBA and/or OBA?	CBA	Frequency (%)	OBA	Frequency (%)
Yes	79	100	15	18,99
No	00	00	64	81,01

Source: Field survey, 2020

According to Table 5, all respondents use CBA and fifteen (15) of them apply both approaches, i.e. a pedagogy based on both CBA and OBA.

This non-conventional approach is a brainchild of some teachers, who apply it to their students without the approval of the education authorities. For them, OBA has positive aspects that need to be emphasised by combining them with the principles of CBA to boost learning.

Also, during the interview with the head of Pedagogy and Continuing Education Office (PCEO) of Abidjan 4, he maintained that "APC is practiced by teachers in all high schools and colleges in the district. This information is verified in Table 5.

Figure 1: Respondents who received specific training on OPP and/or PCA

The number of teachers who have not received specific training in OBA is almost equal to the number of respondents who have received such training. This can be explained by the fact that 27.8% of the respondents have less than 5 years of experience, i.e. they have probably not experienced this pedagogical approach. In addition, there is a group of respondents with [5.10] years of experience.

On the other hand, 87.3% of respondents had already received training in CBA.

In addition to the training provided at INJS, the Pedagogy and Continuing Education Office (PCEO) has taken steps to ensure continuity of work through seminars. The aim is to give beginning teachers a basis for teaching, but also to give everyone new elements for more effective teaching.

As a partial conclusion, we can say that CBA is practised in secondary schools in Abobo by teachers with the required level to use it for teaching.

C- Relationship between CBA and improvement of school results in Physical and Sports Education in terms of knowledge, know-how and interpersonal skills

- Distribution of surveys according to the pedagogical approach used for the first teaching test

“Competency-Based Approach (CBA) and School Results in Physical Education and Sports in Secondary Schools in Côte D’Ivoire”

Figure 2: Pedagogical approach used for the first teaching test

This graph shows that 82.3% and 17.7% of respondents used OBA and the traditional method respectively in the first teaching test.

In fact, the traditional method, which predates OBA, the second great moment in the evolution of Ivorian educational programmes since the colonial era, was not used by any of our respondents. However, some teachers did use it. The analysis showed that these were teachers with less than five years' experience. We can therefore argue that they chose it by pure chance because they had no idea of either.

Table 6: Number of years of experience of respondents

Number of Years of experience	Number	Frequencies (%)
Less than 5 years	22	27,8
5-10 years	30	38,0
11-18 years	10	12,7
19-25 years	07	08,9
More than 25 years	10	12,7
Total	79	100

Source: Field survey, 2020

More than 72% of the teachers interviewed have at least five (05) years of experience in teaching Physical and Sports Education. Most of them have practised OBA, since CBA, in its evolution through the levels of education, entered the second cycle from 2015.

Table 7: Overall averages according to pedagogical approaches and teaching levels.

Levels of Teaching	Averages with Old Methods	Averages with APC
1 st Form	12,1	13,9
3 rd	11,7	13,7
Total	11,9	13,8

Source: Field survey, 2020

In terms of knowledge, most teachers used integration notebooks in Physical and Sports Education to convey theoretical knowledge about the physical activity practiced. This generally concerned the following points: generalities on the physical activity on the programme, its characteristics, the notions linked to this activity and the rules of practice and safety to be observed. It is therefore now the same theoretical content that is given to all students of the same level regardless of the school they attend; this was not the case with previous approaches. The taxonomical verbs commonly used by teachers in this context are "identify and know". Through this new organisation, CBA makes it possible to improve the academic performance of pupils in terms of knowledge.

In terms of know-how, we note an increase of about 2 points in the average class score in Physical and Sports Education in the entire sample, regardless of the level of instruction considered (6th or 4th grade), when the teacher switches from an old approach (OBA or Traditional Method) to the Competency-Based Approach (CBA). Indeed, there is an increase from 12.1 to 13.9, or 1.8 points on average in the 6th grade and an increase of 2 points in the 4th grade. (According to the data collected).

It can be noted that when the teacher uses CBA, the pupils' academic results are improved in terms of skills. This is due to the fact that CBA promotes active and exploratory learning. This makes it easier for learners to construct knowledge by drawing on their own experiences and worldviews. Interactions with their peers and the teacher also improved their academic performance. These are the students we saw excelling in running, jumping, throwing and floor gymnastics.

D- Relationship Between CBA and the Development of Social skills or Know-how

According to Le Boterf (1995), "competence corresponds to "knowing how to act, i.e. knowing how to integrate, mobilise and transfer a set of resources (knowledge, skills) in a given context in order to deal with the various problems encountered or to carry out a task".

For Philippe Perrenoud (1999), "competence is "a capacity for effective action in the face of a family of situations, which one manages to master because one has both the necessary knowledge and the capacity to mobilise it wisely, in good time, to identify and solve real problems". This skill allows one to deal with complex situations, to provide appropriate solutions without having to resort to pre-programmed answers.

For Jacques Tardif, "a competence is "a complex knowledge-action based on the effective mobilisation and combination of a variety of internal and external resources within a family of situations". Common features emerge from these different definitions.

“Competency-Based Approach (CBA) and School Results in Physical Education and Sports in Secondary Schools in Côte D’Ivoire”

We can therefore retain that competence is developed in a given situation and context and uses different resources by mobilising them to solve a problem.

In the context of our study, the concept of "competence-based approach" refers to the teaching method used by teachers to transmit knowledge, know-how or interpersonal skills and which places the learner at the centre of learning.

It is therefore from 2002 that the CBA will make its gradual entry into Ivorian general education with the aim of reducing repetition and failure at school but also of developing social skills at the level of learners to enable them to cope with the various situations of social life. This new approach is based on the following main objectives :

- The learner is responsible for his/her own learning. The teacher is simply a facilitator;
- The learner learns when he/she is interacting with his/her peers or teacher;
- They learn when their learning is meaningful. In other words, the learner needs to know the purpose of everything he/she learns in school;
- He learns with the help of an adult or from real life experiences.

As regards interpersonal skills, Physical and Sports Education teachers, through the activity practised, teach pupils to respect the rules of hygiene and safety, but also a sense of politeness (saying hello or good evening, raising one's hand to ask to speak, not interrupting someone rudely, knowing how to wait one's turn, knowing how to ask for forgiveness, knowing how to say thank you), and solidarity (accepting a majority decision, accepting that pupils with learning difficulties are given more time, being a team player in games, compromising during the game or being courteous to others). Since the CBA is about acquiring skills, it allows the young person to acquire respect for rules as well as respect for authority and others. Integration into the peer group through negotiation, courtesy and acceptance of others are all significant skills and aptitudes that this approach helps young people acquire during their lessons. Conflict resolution with peers through negotiation is a quality that appeared in the young people taught by the CBA but not in the others who only experienced the OBA. The discovery of a number of skills in students who did CBA as opposed to those who did not was clearly apparent during our study. This approach establishes the teacher as a model of probity accompanying the young person in his or her learning and choices. This approach, by making the young person truly responsible for his or her learning through the personal commitment that he or she is obliged to have, leads him or her to be more mature and to take others into account.

We can rightly argue that the acquisition of these social skills can keep the young person away from marginality, deviance and delinquency. The young person acquires autonomy through PCA and will therefore be better equipped to integrate social laws and understand the need to conform to norms in order to succeed, as proposed by their society (social consensus).

This aspect of the results is an innovation since previous approaches did not take this into account. They were more concerned only with improving outcomes in terms of skills and knowledge without emphasising behavioural or social skills.

To elaborate, of eighty (80) students who were asked about their preference between the first test approach (OBA or traditional approach) and the second test approach (CBA), the answer was always immediate. They all prefer the second test method, i.e. the Competency-Based Approach. Indeed, in the specific case of Physical and Sports Education, this approach allows pupils to show their know-how, sometimes acquired during extra-curricular activities. In football, for example, some pupils have technical and tactical skills as a result of participating in neighbourhood tournaments; limiting them to simple gestures could demotivate them, as was the case with previous pedagogies. CBA allows the teacher to situate his or her pupils in the zone of proximal development (ZPD)¹², one of the conditions for effective teaching.

It can therefore be said that APC makes it possible to improve the academic performance of pupils in terms of knowledge, know-how and interpersonal skills, and thus to better educate them and even equip them (social skills) to better socialise them (hence the relevance of this pedagogical approach to the education process). In the same vision, Xavier or maintains that the CBA "allows the school to better ensure its function of education, socialisation and qualification".

DISCUSSION

The exit profile describes the expectations at the end of a complete cycle of training.

In Physical and Sports Education, for the first cycle, the exit profile is as follows:

At the end of the first cycle of secondary education, the student should have acquired knowledge and built competences enabling him/her to

- Know the rules of the game, the safety and ethical rules related to the practice of physical sports activities (PSA);
- Know the benefits of practising PSA and the rules of hygiene appropriate to these activities;
- Apply and enforce the rules of play, safety, ethics and hygiene;

young person is able to carry out his or her learning alone. On the other hand, there is also a zone of rupture in which he is not able to put into practice.

¹² VIGOTSKY's concept of child development research; consulted at this link <https://www.ac-paris.fr> According to the researcher, this is the zone of autonomy in which the

“Competency-Based Approach (CBA) and School Results in Physical Education and Sports in Secondary Schools in Côte D’Ivoire”

- Plan and execute with peers cooperation and opposition strategies in collective physical and sports activities;
- Plan and execute with peers cooperative and oppositional strategies in group physical activities and sports; Perform a variety of actions in individual or dual physical activities and sports;
- Plan and handle PSA competitions with peers.

As for the second cycle, the output profile in Physical and Sports Education is as follows:

At the end of the second cycle of secondary education, the student must have acquired knowledge and built social skills enabling him/her to

- Engage lucidly in practice: prepare for effort, know their limits, know and control the risks, protect themselves from trauma, recover, appreciate the effects of physical activity on themselves, etc.
- Respect the rules of collective life and assume the different roles linked to the activity: judge, referee, help, parry, observe, appreciate, train, etc.
- Know how to use different approaches to learn to act effectively: observe, identify, analyse, appreciate the effects of the activity, evaluate success and failure, design projects.¹³

The output profiles of this pedagogical approach highlight an incalculable number of social skills, which the young person can acquire in a learning situation¹⁴.

Knowledge and skills are not left out either. CBA, as we have discussed in this study, has advantages and disadvantages according to various previous studies conducted around the world, in the sense of its relevance to the education of young people, through the acquisition of knowledge, know-how and skills. Thus, the hypothesis that CBA brings positive changes in the academic performance of students in Abobo (Côte d'Ivoire) is confirmed. For P. Perrenoud (1998), the aim of CBA is to develop skills at the learners' level to enable them to cope with all situations in social life as observed with our study population. Indeed, using CBA, Physical and Sports Education teachers presented problem situations from social or professional life and asked students to provide appropriate responses. This assertion is in line with Emile Durkheim's statement on pedagogy: "It is a reflection applied as methodically as possible to educational matters"¹⁵. He argues that pedagogy is both a theory, the purpose of which is to reflect on educational systems and processes in order to appreciate their value and to enlighten and direct the action of teachers, and a practice. We read pedagogy or approach as a way of 'passing education' to the young person or learner.

For our study, we can say that pedagogy is the art of teaching, i.e. transmitting knowledge, know-how or interpersonal skills to pupils.

For social life, we observed learners respecting the rules of collective life by accepting, for example, their differences, defeat during competitions, helping each other in groups with the aim of promoting cooperation, and helping the weakest.

In terms of professional life, the teachers' use of problem situations helped to highlight the notions of observation in order to make the right decisions, competitiveness, refereeing, etc. This encouraged the development of skills that are essential to the success of the project. This has encouraged the development of skills in terms of knowledge, know-how and interpersonal skills. The same author, in inviting teachers to reconsider certain aspects of teaching, confirms what we observed in the Abobo schools. These aspects include taking into account knowledge as a resource to be mobilised, teaching based on problem situations and the practice of formative evaluation in work situations.

In addition, during our investigation, we noted that in teaching with CBA, pupils took charge of their own work under the guidance of the teacher. At first, some of them, designated as group leaders, checked the attendance. The second part of a Physical and Sports Education session devoted to the warm-up was still led by them. Thus, these students learn to be leaders, to keep their environment clean, to help others succeed and to accomplish common tasks. This is what X. Roegers (2000) when he states that CBA was born in the world of education in order to make the link between academic achievements and social practices. In the same vein, C. Delorme (2008) maintains that in CBA, the learner must be seen as the agent of his or her own learning. The PES teacher, by applying CBA, engages his or her students, which improves their academic performance and, in turn, their education in terms of knowledge, skills and attitudes.

CONCLUSION

The objective, which was to analyse the relationship between CBA and academic results in Abobo secondary schools in Physical and Sports Education (PSE) in order to show that academic success is a sign of education, which could keep people away from deviance and crime, was achieved. As a methodological approach, a mixed approach was used, notably the quantitative and qualitative method.

This study was conducted in the commune of Abobo, located in the district of Abidjan, and involved

¹³ Retrieved from this search link: The exit profile describes the expectations at the end of a full cycle of training. In PSE, for the first cycle, the exit profile is as follows: At the end of the first cycle of secondary education, the student should have acquired knowledge and skills that will enable him/her to - Search (bing.com)

¹⁴ Sylvie Monchâtre's studies on the APC in Burkina for example. Retrieved from this link: <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-01100078>

¹⁵ DURKHEIM Emile, *l'évolution pédagogique en France*, Paris, PUF, 1938, p.8

seventy-nine (79) physical education and sports teachers. In order to test the hypothesis, we used the experimental method in a natural context and the dialectic according to the idea of reasoning, contradiction and interpretation. As instruments of data collection, we used documentary research, interviews and direct observation. The quantitative method was useful in the statistical processing of the data, while the qualitative method was used for content analysis.

The results showed that the use of CBA favours, on the one hand, the involvement of pupils in the teaching/learning process and, on the other hand, the improvement of their academic performance in terms of knowledge, skills and attitudes. In conclusion, the hypothesis was confirmed since it appears that CBA improves the academic results of the pupils in Physical and Sports Education and therefore favours their better education and even their socialisation.

Cusson's theory of reference is confirmed because it has been clearly demonstrated that the school educates and then becomes a powerful means of preventing deviance and crime through the achievements of family and school education. This is where the originality of our work lies. As no study can be exhaustive, we propose to link this CBA approach to what its method could bring to the treatment of young offenders, under observation in institutions.

REFERENCES

1. CUSSON Maurice, 2015, *La Criminologie*, 6^e édition, éditions Hachette Supérieur.
2. DELORME Charles, 2008, *l'Approche par les Compétences : entre les promesses des déclarations et les réalités du terrain*, CEPEC International.
3. DURKHEIM Emile, 1999, *éducation et sociologie*, éd. Paul Emile Boulet, Canada.
4. DUGRAVIER Romain, Barbey-Mintz Anne-Sophie, « Origines et concepts de la théorie de l'attachement », *Enfances & Psy*, 2015/2 (N° 66), p. 14-22. DOI: 10.3917/ep.066.0014. URL: <https://www.cairn.info/revue-enfances-et-psy-2015-2-page-14.htm>
5. HAMELINE Daniel., *les objectifs pédagogiques*, Paris ESF, 1979
6. KOUDOU Opadou et SEKA Yapi Arsène Thierry, 2021, *La psychologie de l'Education dans la formation des Enseignants*, P 1-34, Presses Universitaires d'Abidjan
7. LE BOTERF, 1995, *De la compétence, essai sur un attracteur étrange*, Paris, Editions d'organisation.
8. PERRENOUD Philippe, *Construire des compétences dès l'école*, Paris 1999, ESF.
9. PERRENOUD Philippe, « l'école saisie par les compétences », intervention au colloque de l'association des cadres scolaires du Québec. « Former des élèves compétents : la pédagogie à la

croisée des chemins », Québec, 9-11 décembre 1998.

10. ROEGERS Xavier, 2000, *une pédagogie de l'intégration*, Bruxelles : De Boeck.
11. TARDIF JACQUES, 2006, conférence du 27 avril 2006 à l'Université de Sherbrooke « l'évaluation des compétences ».